

Lessons Learned from the HawkEye-SeaHawk Mission

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Figure 1. Rendering of SeaHawk above Western Europe.

Abstract

The SeaHawk-HawkEye mission was conceived to launch an ocean color radiometer (HawkEye) on a CubeSat nanosatellite (SeaHawk). The launch in December 2018 followed by operationalization (i.e., demonstration of its ability for fine-pointing, collection of high-quality imagery, transmission to ground stations, and processing to retrieve remote sensing reflectances) in June 2021 proved the concept. HawkEye collected 120 m resolution images at wavelengths and spectral characteristics nearly matching those of the best-in-class SeaWiFS mission.

The original project, named Sustained Ocean Color Observations from Nanosatellites (SOCON) proposed to demonstrate the capabilities of a single or small number of SeaHawk-HawkEye-like instruments while also highlighting the potential scientific gains from a constellation of such satellite-sensor combinations. As such, the HawkEye design information was intended from the start to be readily available, and the team wishes to share lessons learned to save others from our discovered and hypothesized pitfalls.

This paper summarizes issues with HawkEye and SeaHawk where shortcomings were discovered, or where the team did not have the proper experience to evaluate the expected performance on-orbit properly. This is a hodgepodge of issues and does not serve as a comprehensive design document.

Technical Details

For further details regarding the radiometer, the reader is referred to Holmes et al. (2018). Additional information about the mission as well as data can be found via the NASA Ocean Color website at <https://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/about/missions/hawkeye/> (accessed 18-Jul-2018).

Figure 2. Photograph of HawkEye-1 unit next to soda can for scale. Note science apertures on top surface of sensor package.

Radiometry Summary

In Table 1, I present my best knowledge of the calibration of HawkEye at this time, which should apply to all images taken since April 2021. We have a considerable library of images since that time, all at the same exposure times, so this should be useful for any researcher estimating light levels from these images. This estimate includes the degradation estimated from the Lunar Calibration of April 14th, 2022, which was consistent with other data captured over Baja California. Note that there is an adjustment factor to other temperatures (shown), but 10 °C is a good average for orbital operations.

Table 1. Best Unit 2 (In Orbit) Calibration Estimate

Final best calibration estimate of 4/27/2022:										
Using Sphere values of 07/10/2017:										
	Unit 2	Unit 2	Unit 2		Unit 2					Final
	ADU	Sphere	ADU/ms	Response	ADU/ms	Nominal	Actual	Unit 2 ADU	Degradation	Unit 2 ADU
	per ms	Radiance	per	% Change	per	Exposure	Exposure	per	Based on	per
Band	at 35 C		Rad Unit	per Deg C	Rad Unit	(ms)	(ms)	Rad Unit	Lunar	Rad Unit
				at 10 deg C				at 10 deg C	Calibration	at 10 deg C
1	1694	69.53	24.36	0.000	24.36	4.10	4.118	100.30	0.754	75.65
2	3557	121.07	29.38	-0.067	29.87	4.10	4.126	123.25	0.804	99.08
3	9089	200.62	45.30	-0.030	45.64	4.10	4.146	189.21	0.869	164.38
4	12365	249.00	49.66	-0.014	49.83	4.10	4.164	207.51	0.892	185.20
5	20578	365.24	56.34	-0.014	56.53	3.40	3.473	196.34	0.937	184.06
6	34520	643.32	53.66	0.033	53.21	3.40	3.601	191.62	1.000	191.57
7	30865	799.19	38.62	0.065	37.99	4.10	4.384	166.57	0.998	166.24
8	51763	885.96	58.43	0.203	55.46	4.10	4.476	248.23	0.932	231.34

A Rad unit is 1 watt per meter squared per steradian per micron

Specifications

Light Levels

I found that the L_{typical} and L_{max} levels provided in the specification document, *Requirements for an Advanced Ocean Color Radiometer* (Meister et al. 2011), were reasonable. Note that in areas where a lot of mud flows into the ocean the ocean can be almost as bright as desert lands. Table 2 summarizes the radiances I found for typical ocean, land, and maximum brightness clouds, assuming the sun is at the zenith. Big thunderstorms in the tropics have very bright clouds at their centers. The value of this table is that a user may want an instrument which does not saturate on land features, but only on clouds, as HawkEye is currently configured. So, this extra information may be useful.

Table 2. Hawkeye Derived Typical Radiances assuming Clear Skies

Solomon Islands: 4/24/22								
30.51 Angle of sun off zenith in Degrees								
Measured ADU:								
Band	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Jungle Foliage	6178	6968	9039	8555	8249	3254	16310	22273
High Clouds	33685	47567	78875	79753	72631	61470	42978	48281
Blue Water	6384	7024	8837	7537	5198	1982	1031	790
Derived Equatorial Reflectivity:								
Jungle Foliage	16.47	13.15	10.08	8.70	8.82	4.04	28.28	36.16
High Clouds	89.80	89.80	87.99	81.09	77.63	76.23	74.52	78.38
Blue Water	17.02	13.26	9.86	7.66	5.56	2.46	1.79	1.28
Southern California: 4/24/22								
29.53 Angle of sun off zenith in Degrees								
Measured ADU:								
Band	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Light Brown Mohave Desert	8080	11162	18683	19519	21116	22919	17683	21198
Salt Flat	19792	31392	56809	59566	57948	51654	36529	42606
Green Mountains	6127	7348	10166	9808	8995	5360	11846	15488
Los Angeles City	8459	11327	17495	17357	16100	13182	11488	15393
Blue Water	6649	7518	9855	8691	5978	2716	1463	1136
Derived Equatorial Reflectivity:								
Light Brown Mohave Desert	21.33	20.86	20.64	19.65	22.35	28.14	30.36	34.07
Salt Flat	52.24	58.68	62.75	59.97	61.33	63.42	62.72	68.48
Green Mountains	16.17	13.74	11.23	9.87	9.52	6.58	20.34	24.90
Los Angeles City	22.33	21.17	19.33	17.47	17.04	16.19	19.72	24.74
Blue Water	17.55	14.05	10.89	8.75	6.33	3.33	2.51	1.83
Rajkot, India: 4/27/22								
26.68 Angle of sun off zenith in Degrees								
Measured ADU:								
Band	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Salt Flat	19753	30339	53145	54463	55650	50311	32616	34903
Murky Estuary	8442	11597	18896	19270	19311	16620	10400	10341
Sediment Plume	7355	9282	14221	13742	11482	3585	1957	1717
Blue Water	6753	7865	10755	9611	6951	3206	1759	1517
Derived Equatorial Radiances:								
Salt Flat	50.77	55.22	57.17	53.39	57.35	60.16	54.53	54.63
Murky Estuary	21.70	21.11	20.33	18.89	19.90	19.87	17.39	16.19
Sediment Plume	18.91	16.90	15.30	13.47	11.83	4.29	3.27	2.69
Blue Water	17.36	14.32	11.57	9.42	7.16	3.83	2.94	2.37
Bering Strait: 4/19/22								
52.79 Angle of sun off zenith in Degrees								
Measured ADU:								
Band	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Iceberg	19539	29117	49581	49372	45445	38827	26762	28587
Darkest Blue Water	5580	6444	8079	7311	4906	2197	1294	810
Derived Equatorial Reflectivity:								
Iceberg	74.21	78.31	78.80	71.52	69.20	68.59	66.11	66.11
Darkest Blue Water	21.19	17.33	12.84	10.59	7.47	3.88	3.20	1.87
Barents Sea: 7/15/21								
47.33 Angle of sun off zenith in Degrees								
Measured ADU:								
Band	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Green Plankton Bloom	7299	9014	13269	13059	11180	2874	1047	623
Dark Green Forested Land	5315	6288	8218	7661	7111	3532	10257	13102
Light Green Forested Land	5593	6587	8852	8497	8161	4807	10488	14000
High Clouds	22311	32701	55239	55890	52615	44815	32502	36838
Blue Water	5689	6436	8060	7129	4706	1784	961	623
Derived Equatorial Reflectivity:								
Green Plankton Bloom	24.73	21.63	18.82	16.88	15.19	4.53	2.31	1.29
Dark Green Forested Land	18.01	15.09	11.65	9.90	9.66	5.57	22.61	27.04
Light Green Forested Land	18.95	15.81	12.55	10.98	11.09	7.58	23.12	28.89
High Clouds	75.61	78.47	78.33	72.24	71.49	70.64	71.64	76.02
Blue Water	19.28	15.44	11.43	9.21	6.39	2.81	2.12	1.29
Moon at 36 degree phase angle: 4/14/22								
2.43 Estimated multiplier to zero phase angle geometry, ignoring opposition surge effect								
Measured ADU:								
Band	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Bright areas	2600	4189	8263	8679	9299	8810	6415	7774
Derived Reflectivity:								
Bright areas	14.51	16.56	19.30	18.47	20.81	22.87	23.29	26.42

The table lists the reflectivity, compared to an exo-atmospheric Lambertian white surface, assuming the scene has the sun at the zenith. To calculate this correction, I simply divided the values by the cosine of the solar angle off the zenith. This ignores atmospheric transmission, which is a tricky correction to apply since most of the light loss due to atmospheric transmission is scattering. However, the bulk of Hawkeye's data collections occur with a solar zenith angle between 30 and 50 degrees, so the information in Table 2 is good for quick estimation.

Signal to Noise Ratio

When I started this instrument design, I had a strong concern about expecting high resolution and high signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the same time, since the ocean surface has structure at small scales, like whitecaps and sun glint off waves. Not a lot of ocean color instruments have our resolution, so this is an important point. Figure 3 shows the ocean south of Point Conception near Santa Barbara in a recent Band 5 (555 nm) image—very noisy. However, another image south of Mar De Plata, Argentina, was noteworthy since it was so smooth. The color image is shown in Figure 4, and the Band 2 (443 nm) image in Figure 5. Band 5 (555 nm) is shown in Figure 6 at the same contrast setting as the Santa Barbara image. Based on this, I am now a believer that SNR ratios twice as good as HawkEye would not be wasted. For the Argentina snapshots, the SNR was 194:1 for 443 nm, and 166:1 for 555 nm, for a 120 m pixel. This implies an SNR as great as 2000: to 3000:1 for 1 km pixels would sometimes be useful! Notice the reversal of bright and dark areas between Band 2 and Band 5 scenes. The Argentina images also show some radiation hits – small horizontal streaks.

Figure 3. Wind-induced Speckle in the Ocean South of Santa Barbara

Figure 4. Plankton Bloom South of Mar de Plata.

Figure 5. Plankton Bloom at 443 nm.

Figure 6. Plankton Bloom at 555 nm.

Bright Target Recovery/Stray Light

This is a large topic, and a difficult one. After I became famous for failing a bright target recovery specification for SeaWiFS that required expensive rework, I became very sensitive to this issue. The issue arose since CZCS had a problem where a bright region in the scanned scene could saturate the pre-amp, and the amplifier took most of the scan line to recover, corrupting the data. I was on unfamiliar ground here with a refractive design, as opposed to one using off-axis mirrors like other instruments. The specification, *Requirements for an Advanced Ocean Color Radiometer* (Meister et al. 2011), which I helped write, stated that the instrument in the near infrared bands should have stray light of about 0.2% of L_{typical} for an L_{max} 50X greater than L_{typ} , which is a ratio of 0.004%, at a distance of 4 pixels (using for that specification 1 km pixels). For HawkEye this is 30 pixels. I have looked at many images trying to find scenes that would allow me to evaluate the performance of the instrument from orbit. The ideal target to assess stray light from orbit is a nice big, isolated iceberg floating in sterile waters in good weather. Those are hard to capture. Shorelines in general are problematic since the water is shallow near the coast and you may be seeing the bottom or sediment. Clouds tend to have fuzzy edges and are not often isolated. Figure 7 shows a snow-covered island in Antarctica captured in January 2022 with HawkEye. This was the best target I could find. Figure 8 shows the measured stray light near the east edge of the island. This may be showing my bright target recovery, but a complicating factor is snow fields reflect almost as much sunlight up as is coming down. Rayleigh scattering of the upward reflected light occurs, so the atmosphere is naturally brighter near the island due to this.

Figure 7. Isolated Antarctic Island, shown with Normal and High Contrast. Red line indicates portion of image used for analysis in Figure 8

Figure 8. Measured Edge Fall-off near Snow-Covered Island using data depicted in Figure 7

Fortunately, I have calibration data where I viewed an integrating sphere at some distance away in a dark room. Figure 9 shows the stray light near the edge of the imaged sphere aperture. This is more representative of what is possible with a small lens system.

Figure 9. Calibration Measurement of Edge Fall-Off

Considering our IFOV is much smaller than MODIS, the HawkEye data shown in Figure 8 is comparable to MODIS in performance at the same physical distance from the edge. Since the specification (Meister et al. 2011) was written assuming larger pixels, I had no guidance as to how good was good enough. My estimate from orbital data is that Hawkeye exceeds Gerhard's specification by at least 10X in our best direction for Band 8 (865 nm) at 30 pixels. But that may be the scene, not the instrument. Our lab testing indicates Band 8 was at 4X Gerhard's spec, at 30 pixels. My final point here is this is a complicated issue, with serious design impacts, and needs further clarification.

Polarization

The Hawkeye OnSemi KLI-4104 CCDs I used had about 3% polarization sensitivity on-axis, and 4% at 20 degrees off-axis. I was not expecting this, and it forced me to add a polarization scrambler, which led to other problems. The polarization sensitivity was greatest in the near IR. I would have had a cleaner design if we could have just lived with the polarization sensitivity since it was small. Most of the polarization in the scene is due to Rayleigh scattering, and should be predictable with modeling, and corrected numerically. Sun glint is problematic though and must be avoided by choosing the collection geometry.

Fabrication

Envelope

One particularly challenging part of developing the HawkEye was that there was not from the start a well well-defined envelope (i.e., maximum allowable space with constrained geometry inside the spacecraft).

We were trying to fit a lot of instrument in a 10 cm cube, and every millimeter mattered. As sensor and spacecraft designs iterated, we kept getting squeezed because it was determined that there was a need for an exterior skin over all sides of the instrument, and other constraints. We had to shrink our exterior dimensions twice because of the changing envelope.

Surge Current

At the beginning of the program, we assumed since we were battery powered high momentary currents were not important. However, the batteries used by Clyde Space had significant internal resistance, and we had to control start-up peak currents to avoid causing the battery voltage to drop too low and reset the spacecraft computer. My electrical engineer spent considerable time modeling in-rush currents to accommodate this. We were successful, but a CubeSat program run by students could step into a BIG problem with this issue.

Board Design

We used very thick ground and power planes in our circuit boards to provide heat conduction to the outer structure. As a result, the boards were heavy, and could not be soldered normally. We had to mount a heater and fan under the boards to preheat them to allow soldering, all while under a stereo microscope.

Centering Small Lenses

I am an optical engineer by training, but I had little experience with bonding small lenses into barrels. We used 2216 epoxy to spot glue the glass into stainless steel barrels, for best thermal expansion matching. To center the lenses into the barrels, which is critical, we made a fixture to spin the lenses underneath a microscope and I would observe reflections off the element, and manually tweak the centering to stop the reflections from nutating. Since I had to do three lenses per lens barrel, and 24 barrels, this was tedious. Hawkeye in-orbit focus quality varies from edge to edge for different bands, so I did not center the lenses as well as I wished to, even though I was careful. For future instruments, this issue would need to be improved.

Focus Quality

Each band was focused visually by looking through the lens with an external telescope focused at infinity and viewing the CCD structure lit through the lens. This worked OK, but was deficient in that my lens system had substantial residual chromatic aberration, so the focus varied with wavelength. So, after visual focusing, I had to offset most of the lenses by rotating the lens barrel in its threads by a predetermined amount. I also had to add in a bit extra to best balance the center to edge focus variation. For Unit Two, the instrument in orbit, I think I forgot this second step, so our focus is great on-axis, but a bit too soft at the edges. In retrospect, perhaps this may have been the best choice.

Cleanliness

Our shutter is a thin sheet of anodized aluminum sliding on loose-fitting stainless-steel pins. Initially we thought we would get away with this, but we discovered after hundreds of cycles the sliding was not as smooth as when new and developed a gritty feel. So, we needed some sort of lubrication. I chose to use a molybdenum disulfide lubricant very sparingly that could be applied to the aluminum. However, even though it came in liquid form, it was basically a suspension of fine particles. Since the shutter was right above our windowless CCDs, particles were a huge concern. I ended up scrubbing the lubricant into the aluminum holes with a wooden stick, to try and embed the particles into the aluminum, and carefully cleaning off the excess. We then ran the shutters for 1000 cycles and blew out the cavity and tried to get it as clean as possible. We ended up with very few particles being deposited during launch across all 8

bands – only around 10. If we did this again, I would try harder to find some other coating for the aluminum!

Shutter Deformation

Our shutter was driven by solenoids that slammed the shutter back and forth using a pin through a hole in the shutter. We discovered after hundreds of cycles that the hole was deforming from the high G-forces that occurred as the shutter stopped. So, we added a thin rubber O-ring to the pivot shaft of the shutter solenoid mechanism to reduce these high peak forces. It seemed to work, but it was critical to use an O-ring that worked over a wide temperature range. As of this time, the shutter has worked 1000 times before the instrument was shipped, and 4000 times since, so it seems to be stable. We did have about 2X margin on this mechanism, but its reliability was a source of concern.

On-Orbit

Stability

The directional stability of the instrument is essential to successfully aggregate multiple lines of data together to improve the signal to noise ratio. HawkEye was intended to sum 3 lines of data together separated by 18 pixels total. So, we needed stability on the order of ± 1 pixel over 0.335 seconds. This works out to about ± 0.04 degrees per second, the maximum drift acceptable in roll or pitch. Yaw is a bit more tolerant. Since our exposure is 110 seconds long, that is a maximum drift of ± 4.4 degrees over an exposure. Another metric is the error between Finderscope frames, which are 4.45 seconds apart. An acceptable error would be 0.18 degrees between Finderscope frames. As you can see in Figure 10, the instrument stability is close to this—within a factor of two. However, when we have an “excursion” from nominal pointing, the blur is cosmetically objectionable, so we have taken most images without aggregation. We get sudden roll shifts when the corresponding reaction wheel crosses through zero speed.

Figure 10. Spacecraft Stability Measured by Reviewing Finderscope Data.

Thermal

In reviewing Hawkeye temperature data, I find that the instrument starting temperature varies from about 0–18 °C when viewing scenes ranging from Greenland to Australia, or Maine to Antarctica, about 100 degrees of latitude. Since the instrument is in the sun for more than 180 degrees of latitude, this implies we get orbital temperature swings of around 32 °C, from -7–25 °C. This is a big thermal cycle for an instrument. We tested operation during qualification from -20–60 °C.

Signal to Noise (SNR) Performance

Our signal to noise estimates pre-launch were accurate. For all conditions the signal to noise ratio is equal to the square root of the captured electrons per pixel. Our electronic gain is 2.0 electrons per ADU. Pattern noise does not seem to limit summing multiple pixels together to improve the SNR, at least up to 8x8. The only sensitivity we have seen to radiation in orbit is the occasional bright pixel, usually two or three pixels in a horizontal row. In the South Atlantic anomaly, we might get a dozen across a 1818x6000 pixel scene, per band. They can be a nuisance when they land in the dark field portion of the image at the bottom of each band, since that will make the dark appear too high, causing a dark streak in the band after subtraction. A median filter fixes such problems easily.

Residual Striping

With a pushbroom array, one worries about striping in the image due to detector-to-detector response variations. Figure 11 shows what our Band 5 striping looks like before and after applying a flat field correction, displayed with 10% contrast full scale, for a scene in Antarctica containing a particularly featureless iceberg.

Figure 11. Antarctica Iceberg, shown with and without Flat Fielding.

The rms variation of the vertical striping in this figure goes from 0.36% for the un-flat fielded image to 0.074% for the flat-fielded image. This implies my use of a pushbroom array scanner limits the signal to noise ratio to 1350:1, much better than my SNR for considerably dimmer ocean radiances, justifying this choice.

Bilinear Gain Knee

HawkEye uses a bilinear compression scheme to reduce the bit depth for transmission to the ground. For CCD-type detectors, which usually have a noise equal to the square root of the detected photoelectrons, higher signal means higher noise. So, at low levels we send the total ADU down as detected, but at higher levels we compress it by dividing by a factor of two to four. This compression is done on orbit, and the knee data returned with every image, where decompression is applied automatically. The scheme has worked well, and we have seen no evidence of any artifact associated with the knee in the data at all.

Filter Ghosts

I discovered late in the fabrication that the Hawkeye filters produced ghosts. The filters were 3 mm thick, and I had them polished flat and parallel before final coating to guarantee that I would not have ghosts off the surfaces, but, unknown to me, the filters were fabricated from multiple thin layers of filter glass glued together to improve the out-of-band blocking. The internal layers were not exactly parallel to the outer surfaces – a wedge of 100 microns across the filter would produce a reflection displaced about 60 pixels off the parent beam. The ghosts have an intensity of about 1%, worst case. Figure 12 shows an image of icebergs floating in the Bering Strait with normal contrast and with the contrast pushed so 5% is full scale. The ghosts are apparent above and below the ice sheets. The ghost for every band is different. Digital processing could reduce this effect, since it was well measured during calibration, but spacecraft stability is not perfect, limiting the success of such processing. I could have solved this problem by spending about \$60,000 and 4 months of schedule time, and had filters fabricated that were plane parallel with no internal layers, with coatings only on the outer edges. Out-of-band leakage might not have been as good, though. In processing images from orbit, I have seldom noticed this effect since clouds and coastlines do not have such dramatic gradients as my iceberg scene.

Figure 12. Icebergs Floating in the Bering Strait, Illustrating Filter Ghosts (Band 5 – 555nm)

The question of how sharp of an edge one could expect to achieve is a fair one. Several figures are shown above when discussing bright target recovery that provided some data. The Band 8 data for this iceberg (Figure 12) in the Bering Strait is a good test on the west (left) edge since there is very little Rayleigh scattering and the filter ghost is small. Figure 13 shows the profile near this edge. The data for Band 3 shown before in Figure 9 was better, but that was measured in a lab, and not from orbit with an aging instrument after 3.5 years in orbit.

Figure 13. Sharpest Edge from Orbit in Absence of Filter Ghosts.

The reason sharp edges are needed in ocean color is to allow collection of good data in close to a coastline or where scenes with fields of clouds are quite common, as in the tropics. For example, Figure 14 shows a Band 8 image of the ocean near the Solomon Islands. Figure 15 shows what a 5 pixel-tall slice through the scattered cloud field looks like, using a logarithmic scale. Since 1.0 on this scale is 31,000 ADU, and the ocean brightness averages around 860 ADU, we need to reach levels of around 0.0025 to be able to measure with 10% accuracy between clouds. Even this band cannot reach these levels since the clouds are only one or two kilometers apart. Or, perhaps humidity levels, and therefore aerosol scattering, are elevated between clouds? Since this is a challenging specification, it would be worthwhile to answer this question of how good is good enough.

Figure 14. Field of Small Clouds near Solomon Island

Figure 15. Slice of Data through Cloud Field near Solomon Islands

Scrambler Ghosts

A design mistake was made with HawkEye. Both the filters and the scrambler were tilted, in opposite directions, in the along track direction. I did this to make sure that light reflecting off the detector array metallization would not be reflected into the system where it would be seen as a ghost. Fortunately, that part of my thinking appears to have worked. But what I did not consider was that the reflections off the filter, at the edges of the passband, could be reflected off the scrambler and back into the system to produce a focused, sharp ghost image. Had the baffle in front of the lens system been longer, this would not have produced a ghost either, but here I had no available space. I knew about this ghost during assembly and calibration, and measured it, but it was only about 0.1% in magnitude, so I thought it was acceptable. However, it appears that my antireflection coatings have eroded over time in orbit, and at this writing (1-May-2022) the ghost is about 1% and seems stable. Figure 16 shows the impact of the ghost on the images.

Addendum (3-Jul-2024): I have since learned that my scrambler ghost is almost certainly due to the MgF_2 antireflection coating on the scrambler outside surface eroding away. In general, filter coatings have trouble with the orbital environment. The right answer is to use an uncoated fused silica surface as your outermost surface and orient it so the 1% ghost generated is very close to the original scene features so it can be corrected by a simple subtraction/deconvolution technique. 1% is a bad ghost—do not assume it is negligible when doing ocean color.

Figure 16. Scrambler Ghost in Mallorca Band 7 (751 nm) Image.

I consider the ghost in Figure 16 unacceptable. Of course, when there are lots of clouds there are lots of cloud ghosts all over the image. In retrospect, if I had used a double prism scrambler (a few more mm thicker) the ghost would have been much closer to the parent, and digital processing could have been employed without stability being such an issue.

The ghost appears to be worst in Bands 7 and 8, and this was a different AR coating than for the other bands. Consequently, the ocean color processing uses Band 6 (670 nm) for aerosol correction, which reduces the impact of the ghost; however, using Bands 7 and 8 may have improved atmospheric correction in general, especially in turbid waters.

It is important for any instrument designer reading this report to realize that narrow optical filters, commonly used to define the passband, have a region at the edge spectrally where the transmission is around 50%. What one tends to forget is that the reflectivity at that region is also around 50%, since the dichroic coatings have little absorption. Sharp transitions at the spectral edges help, but you will always end up with a lot of light reflected out of the system. The problem is that if anything returns this light back into the system, the transmission to the stray light is about 50%. Beware!

Diffuse Stray Light

I worried a great deal about diffuse stray light during the design of the instrument. The concern is that very low levels of stray light, far from the parent source, can sum up to several percent of the measured ocean brightness. This is very tough to measure during calibration, since we are talking about levels

10,000 to 100,000 times below the input source. I had a very cramped instrument space, so it was hard to put baffles between neighboring bands, and blackened baffles have some reflectivity too, and can produce a problem. In the end, I have no baffles between bands, merely horizontal planes parallel to the CCDs, except for the shutter. This approach seems to work well, but it is tough to measure this effect in orbit as well. To quantify it, I looked at a large hole in the ice pack in an image of the Bering Strait and compared it to a featureless scene east of Southern Argentina. Both were at similar sun angles. Figure 17 shows the “Excess” water reflectivity found for the Bering Strait image, which I presume is a worst-case measurement of the diffuse scatter. This ranges from 13% (in the blue) to 75% (in the near IR) of the signal from the ocean itself! This is for an instrument that has been in space for 3.5 years with no optics protection. I am not extremely confident in this measurement since there were some nearby plankton blooms in the Southern Ocean, and potentially unknown blooms in the Bering Strait, or floating small ice. In ocean color analysis such a diffuse stray light looks a lot like aerosol and may not affect the chlorophyll result much. However, I can envision a problem when you have a bright coastline on one side of the image and not on the other since the stray light corruption could have a gradient or vary from band to band. In the near IR, I chose a portion of the Bering Strait scene that did not appear to be corrupted by the scrambler ghost.

Figure 17. Worst Case Diffuse Stray Light Measurement.

Flat Fields

I captured flat fields with the instrument using a NASA-provided 12 inch integrating sphere with a 4” aperture. My lenses were close enough together so that I could capture all bands at once. I worried about light reflected off the instrument corrupting the sphere light level uniformity since it was only a few inches from the aperture, but the front of the instrument was painted black, and reflected little light back into the sphere. However, it seems that the sphere was not as uniform as needed, and there is a gradient in the sphere brightness. This was determined by scanning the instrument field of view across the sphere while collecting data. The discrepancy was a few percent—enough to show up in the ocean color chlorophyll data since not every band’s gradients are the same.

We confirmed this by capturing 4 images of the Namibia desert over 5 days and comparing land brightness values for the same location on Earth, but which appeared at different positions across the

frame. I then went back and analyzed scanned versus static flat field data, which corroborated the Namibia data. The gradients discovered are illustrated in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Gradients Derived from Scene Data.

Sediment versus Plankton

I have looked at quite a few images to discern how ocean color researchers can distinguish plankton from sediment using spectral data. I have also measured plankton samples with my homemade spectrograph equipment. I came out of this convinced that the existing algorithms don't work that well. They do work after a fashion but with huge errors bars. Both sediment and plankton are green in images from space due to water absorption. I believe that additional bands around the chlorophyll fluorescence feature at 685 nm, also near where the reflectivity for green plants changes sharply with wavelength, would be very helpful (e.g., following the fluorescence line height method (Behrenfeld et al. 2009)). This is a spectrally complex region if there is organic matter, but very simple if the water merely has sediment. It deserves a close look. Also, the pair of bands at 490 and 510 nm did not seem to work very well for detecting chlorophyll absorption. I found myself wishing the 510 nm band was 685 nm instead!

Figure 19. Louisiana Coast captured on April 22nd-23rd, 2022. Sediment or Plankton?

Parting Thoughts

In the period since we last built the instrument the CCD vendor we used, OnSemi, has obsoleted the old Kodak CCD line, including the linear array we used in Hawkeye. If we were to try to make another one, I would have to use another device with different properties, from someone else. I suspect several of our electronic components have gone obsolete as well. Researchers should realize that any electronic device sold in small volumes is very much at the mercy of a rapidly evolving electronics industry, and you are almost forced to do a lifetime buy to guarantee parts. However, Hawkeye did prove that good ocean color data can be collected by a very small, inexpensive instrument. I hope that the problems I summarized in this paper will help the next designer avoid some of these issues, and not have to get older to get smarter!

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